

VALENCE COMPOSITION OF VERBS OF ACTION

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Abstract: In this article, there are opinions about the expression of valence structure in verbs of action in linguistics and the features of valence.

Key words: action verbs, valence, lexical valence, denotative meaning, significative, lexeme.

As a work of deep analysis of action verbs in Uzbek linguistics, G. We should mention Q.Mirsanov's candidate's dissertation entitled "*Actional and aspectual features of verbs of movement in English and Uzbek*". The author divided Uzbek verbs of movement into lexical-semantic groups and tried to determine their actional (boundedness/unboundedness, limiting neutral) characteristics. These action features serve to fully reveal the aspectual meanings of complex compounds in the interconnection of analytical forms.¹ In the scientist's classification, the verbs in the Uzbek language with the characteristic of limitation appear as follows:

❖ *verbs of direction to the speaker or object: to come, to enter, to approach, to reach, to return, etc.*

❖ *action verbs expressing the meaning of "moving away" from the object: to go, to depart, to go, to go out, to retreat, to get away, to go away and to set off, to set out, to set off's;*

❖ *verbs meaning "to pass" from the object: to pass, to increase, etc.*

❖ *verbs of one action: go out, enter;*

2. *To the group of verbs with two action characteristics:*

➤ *verbs indicating the subject's movement in space: walk, swim, fly;*

➤ *verbs to run and run, denoting intensive movement;*

3. *Verbs of action with unlimited actional semantics indicate the manner of action:*

✓ *crawl, stand, crawl, etc.;*

✓ *non-directional movement of movement in a wide space: walking, wandering, etc.*²

According to the author's classification, the verb "to leave" is included in the group of single-action verbs. Also, the researcher included the finger, which

¹ Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

² Мирсанов Ғ.Қ. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида юриш-ҳаракат феълларининг акционал ва аспектуал хусусиятлари: Филол. фан. номз. дисс. — Самарқанд, 2009. — 155 б.

belongs to the group of verbs with two action characteristics, to the group of verbs expressing the meaning of "moving away" from the object.

The combined verbs to get on the road, to go on the road, and to go on the road given in the classification can express the meaning of approaching or moving away from the object. The scientist says that the action feature of Uzbek verbs can affect the grammatical form. In particular, action verbs with non-limiting characteristics cannot form an analytical form in a morphological argument. In the sentence, they express the manner and method of the subject's action only in the adverbial function. We will consider this opinion of the author through our own examples. For example: I am most interested in the fact that the old man is not afraid of camels. He walks freely among the restless camels.³

Linguistic unit also has such a possibility of merging, it (*that is, valence*) also lives in the minds of members of a particular language community with linguistic units. For example, the lexeme [oqi] exists in a person's mind with several empty places, and it can appear in speech and attract as many associates at the same time.

In this case, the interrogative pronouns refer to the words that can be combined with the lexeme [oqi]. This possibility is not given in direct observation and is hidden in the essence of the lexeme [arrow]. But in the speech combinations of reading a book, reading every day, and reading a lot, these possibilities are realized one by one.

Valences of a lexeme can be narrow or wide. For example: the valence complement of the lexeme [hangramoq], which is the answer to the question of what - lexemes [ass], [colt], [hangi]. The elements that complement this valence of the lexeme [kishnamoq] are the lexemes [horse], [toy], [bedov], [saman]. Sometimes connecting or connecting lexemes can form a combination in speech if their meanings are not compatible. For example, Artist "hangradi". In this case, the normative valence is manifested in a broken state, and a portable, figurative meaning emerges. But this purely speech phenomenon did not take place in the linguistic essence of the lexemes [hangra] and [artist]. Because the semantic composition of the lexeme [artist] is "artist", "singing-theatre" themes, it does not have the "hangra" theme, the lexeme [hangramoq] is "donkey", "sounding" has a meaning, it does not contain "artistic" and "singing" meaning fragments.

We tried to prove the lexical valence based on the sample taken from the noun and verb group. But linguistic-lexical valence is characteristic not only of nouns or verbs, but also of other word groups.

³ Ойбек. Болалик — Т.: Ўқитувчи, 1979. — 271 б.

Syntactic valency. Syntactic valence is the second side of lexeme valence, which requires that a lexeme in the dominant position receives subordinate lexemes in a certain syntactic form - agreement, auxiliary, adverbial, adjectival suffix. This governor is determined by the syntactic position and grammatical form of the lexeme. For example, the grammatical form of the words (khatni) and (khat) in the syntactic devices Khatni wrote, Khat wrote is determined by the grammatical form of the main word.⁴

Although lexical and syntactic valence are interrelated, they often change. For example, in the Ashulachi "hangradi" combination, the syntactic valency is unchanged, but the lexical valency is updated. Such a situation indicates that a figurative meaning has emerged. In the conjugations letter wrote, the semantic valence is in place, but the syntactic valence has changed. This shows that different syntactic forms have occurred. However, both of these changes are one-sided - either spiritual or syntactic in nature. What if the change is both lexical and syntactic. This is where the derivation takes place.

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